

“RESEARCH-BASED TRANSFORMATION OF TEACHER EDUCATION: TRADITION AS A BASIS FOR INNOVATION” International Conference on Teacher Education

HOW TO LEARN A NEW LANGUAGE

Yulduz Yangiboyeva Ortiq qizi,
2nd year student of UZSWLU

Supervisor:
Shohida Kasimova Shokir qizi

***Abstract.** Learning a new language is challenging and requires careful planning to achieve success. This thesis aims to explore the various factors that contribute to effective language learning, with a focus on motivation and monitoring. By understanding these key elements, language learners can develop effective strategies to enhance their language acquisition skills. Firstly, students know their motivation and goals. The next important thing is their language levels.*

***Keywords:** Intrinsic motivation, extrinsic motivation, monitoring, input, Language Learning.*

Learning languages can open doors to new cultures, opportunities, and experiences. However, language acquisition is a challenging task which requires dedication and motivation. Most students struggle to learn a new language because they lack information on how to do it. Finding answers to the following questions can solve this problem:

What is your motivation for learning the language?

What is your language level?

What is your weak point in learning a language?

Moreover, in this thesis, I will explore the various methods and techniques that can help people successfully master a foreign language.

Motivation is the most important thing to learn a new language. Vallerand (1997, as cited in Dörnyei, 1998) reported that motivation has been divided into intrinsic and extrinsic in more 800 publications. Intrinsic motivation refers to engaging in a behavior because it is personally rewarding. Extrinsic motivation involves engaging in a behavior to earn reward. Intrinsic motivation is long lasting than extrinsic motivation. However, there are some methods not to lose your motivation through learning process. The first one is to understand your reasons to learn English. Whether it is for study, career, travelling, or personal growth, having a clear goal in mind will provide a sense of direction and help you stay motivated. Secondly, you should establish clear and achievable language learning goals. Defining specific objectives helps learners not only stay motivated but also measure their progress effectively.

In addition to motivation, input is another aspect of language learning. Input refers to the learners' exposure to the target language through various sources, such as reading books, listening to conversations, and watching videos. According to

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Krashen's (1985, p. 82) input hypothesis, language acquisition occurs when learners are exposed to comprehensible input that is one level higher than their current level of proficiency. This means that learners can understand the language input using context and contextual clues, even if they do not know all the words or grammar rules. By increasing their exposure to meaningful input, learners can improve their language skills and gradually internalize language patterns.

Furthermore, the plus one hypothesis proposes that language learners should challenge themselves by adding one new concept to their existing knowledge base. With this incremental approach, learners can gradually expand their language skills. For instance, students can set specific goals, such as learning a new vocabulary word each day and practicing using a new grammar structure in a sentence. By pushing themselves beyond their comfort zone and adding new elements to their language repertoire, learners can make steady progress in their language learning process.

Monitoring is another important part of language learning, which requires self-assessment and reflection on one's language abilities. Krashen (1985) mentioned that to use the monitor, the performer must fulfill two requirements: first, they must be aware of the rule, and second, they must be deliberately concerned with accuracy. It's challenging to fulfill these two requirements. Learners can monitor their language learning by setting specific goals, tracking their daily language practice, and identifying areas for improvement. Regular language monitoring helps learners identify their strengths and weaknesses and measure their progress over time. This self-regulatory process helps learners maintain a sense of control over their learning journey.

In conclusion, learning a new language is a complex and dynamic process that requires motivation, input, and monitoring. To enhance language acquisition skills, students should cultivate intrinsic motivation, challenge themselves with new language elements, and monitor their language progress. These things can help students achieve greater fluency and proficiency.

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